

**RESTORATIVE JUSTICE, A POSSIBILITY THROUGH THE
ADOPTION OF RELIGIOUS PRECEPTS IN HUMAN LIFE: THE
LAICITY OF THE STATE AND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE
RIGHT TO BELIEVE AS A HUMAN RIGHT**

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Abstract: Human beings persistently seek Justice and this reality is in line with the objective of this research work, which is to demonstrate that this ideal can find a solution through the adoption of Restorative Justice based on the religious precepts that it freely and freely adopts. conscious, present in society from a Right of Belief that makes effective a Human Right advocated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, therefore, always to be respected. What justifies the work is the fact that the State, having secularism as its characteristic, must accept the freedom of belief and, therefore, the use of its values when applying the Law so that there is Justice. To demonstrate that such a reality is possible, the methodology used was abduction, through the adoption of a bibliographic research method in theoretical references able to support textual arguments. The intended result was achieved, as it was found that Restorative Justice, based on the religious principles that underlie it, is capable of promoting the rescue of the dignity of the human person when effectively applied. It is noteworthy that the present research did not intend to exhaust the proposed theme, but simply to promote the expansion of debates in academic spaces.

Keywords: Restorative Justice 1. Religious Precepts 2. Secular State 3. Human Rights 4. Constitutional Principles 5.

1 INTRODUCTION

And He will stand and feed the people in the strength of the Lord, in the excellency of the name of the Lord their God. Micah 5:4

Human coexistence is characterized by the successive use of choices, however, many of them lead to the occurrence of injuries to the rights of third parties, since they occur from

relationships established between human beings. When free will leads to extrapolation of limits to the point of causing injury to another individual, the right is invited to manifest itself and a sanction is usually attributed to the person causing the damage. Many of these sanctions do not lead to reflection, to the understanding that there was an intrusion into the sphere of others, causing discontent and damage, not becoming effective in actually reintegrating the individual into a harmonious social coexistence.

When practicing the action that leads to the conflict of interest in relation to the right affected, both parties are convinced that the right belongs to them and for that reason, they impose their position on the other to the point of causing injury, however, their reparation is not it occurs from the sphere of conscience that would provoke changes in behavior and pre-established paradigms, but rather, by the imposition of penalty resulting from legally permitted state coercion.

In the search for an alternative approach to the possibility of achieving the desired Justice in the face of such positions, the proposed theme recognizes the problem and proposes the adoption of Restorative Justice as a solution, which justifies the present research. This in turn, in order to be possible and effective, demands the adoption of values, found in religious precepts, as they are capable of provoking such reflections.

What guarantees that Restorative Justice can be applied are the intrinsic values that compose it and, which have their origin in religion; being the secular State, it must guarantee freedom of belief and, therefore, make possible the application of the Law based on such principles, being this Right of Belief a Human Right, which assists everyone to the extent of their citizenship and also, by the fact to guarantee respect for the fundamental constitutional principle that is the dignity of the human person.

For that, the research is presented with the definition of Restorative Justice and the appointment of the principles that guide it as a result of religious values; after, it was tried to demonstrate the role of the State as the one that guarantees that the constitutional principles prevail and in particular that the state secularism brings the possibility of the exercise and application of the Law from the religious precepts, for being able to guarantee the rescue of beings humans who got lost in their choices, causing injuries to others.

The methodological path used for the development of the research was abduction (CARVALHO, 2013, p. 54/60), based on Semiotics (PEIRCE, 2015, 352p.), for that purpose, having been used as a bibliographic method through consultation to theoretical references, able to substantiate the arguments presented, such as doctrines, articles from periodicals, magazines, newspapers and the database, and also to the relevant legislation and able to subsidize the

textual construction presented, in addition to compliance with technical standards relevant (PRODANOV and FREITAS, 2013).

However, it must be considered that, even backed by theoretical references that provide them with the necessary foundations, the research never had the pretension of presenting itself as absolute, exhausting the theme, but rather expanding the academic spaces of discussion to enable the necessary reflection to everyone dealing with the law.

2 Restorative Justice: a proposal to be considered

Although it no longer composes the structure of the State, religion still occupies an important place in the lives of most Brazilian people, who in their structural human condition demand the presence of a belief because it is a value (STRECK, 2004) that precedes to the Constitution itself, mainly with regard to bringing balance in relationships, being in some circumstances the condition for it to become possible to experience restorative justice in practice.

In the construction of human history, we can always envision a “hybridization” (LENÁ, 1999) and this multiplicity makes it necessary for the exercise of religious belief to be cultivated, mainly, with the State exercising its role, which is to respect and guarantee freedom of choice in the face of religious diversity (CECCHETTI and OLIVEIRA, 2015), therefore, respecting the Constitution and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The Federal Constitution in its art. 5, item VI, provides that freedom of conscience and belief is inviolable, ensuring the free exercise of religious cults and guaranteeing, in accordance with the law, the protection of places of worship and their liturgies, corroborating what is stated in art. . 18 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

The effectiveness of Restorative Justice is manifested when it makes it possible to rescue human beings, especially in their relationships with others (ELLIOTT, 2018), which can only be given with respect for values that have a representativeness of their culture, in this case the Right or Freedom of religious belief based on the experiences that you carry with you through generations.

Human beings already find an established order, whether of the cosmos, society, the State, Law or Religion, but these orders must coexist and be humanely observed so that it can lead human beings to live with dignity, seeking the composition so that there is the overcoming of ills, damages and other misfortunes typical of the human condition, corroborating such aspects ALMEIDA, 2015, p.55, teaches that:

“Keep order, and order will keep you”, or as they say in Latin: *Serva ordinem, et ordo servabit te*. It seems hard to believe, but that's how it is. People who are polarized, obsessed, or, at the other extreme, anarchic, averse to any semblance of discipline, are people doomed to failure, if not global, then with partial certainty; at least, they fall short of the extent of what they could yield for their own benefit and, with more serious repercussions, of their mission as heads or members of a family, as living cells of society for their professional work, for the exemplary spirit in fulfilling their particular civic duties.

Taking into account the proposal for a Restorative Justice, the secular State guarantees the citizen that he can choose to live from his faith, his beliefs and then be able to have principles that allow him to belong to a community, without the imposition of the State. , while awakening a sense of fraternity (DWORKIN, 2014).

The legal system has a structure, based on the Federal Constitution, which, in addition to protecting the Law and freedom of religious belief, has elevated it to a Human Right, since Brazil is a signatory to the Declaration of Human Rights, bringing from it, its values. , among others, the Human Right to have and be able to choose a religious belief to follow, as can be seen from its art. 18:

Everyone has the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion; this right implies freedom to change one's religion or belief, as well as freedom to manifest one's religion or belief, alone or in common, both in public and in private, through teaching, practice, worship and rites.

Such reality presupposes the Law, not only to choose what to believe, but how to believe, in the sense of worship and in what way to express oneself, however, even with the existence of explicit legal regulation, it is not always respected, leading to the Judiciary and, therefore, as a representative of the State, having to express itself in this regard, having to guarantee such freedom.

Therefore, the role played by religion, with regard to helping to have a Restorative Justice, has the condition of reconnecting one human being to another (CURY, 2004), making it possible to overlook situations of displeasure, by recognizing oneself as human, in the humanization that there is in the other, as recognized by MÃE, 2015, p. 15:

Humanity begins with those around you, not exactly with you. Being a person implies your mother, our people, a stranger or your expectation. With no one in the present or the future, the individual thinks as unreasonably as the fish do. It lasts for whatever ingenuity it has and seems like an undifferentiated attribute of the planet. It looks like anything.

Therefore, recognizing oneself as human in the humanization present in the other is to admit mistakes, not excluding, but trying to help, especially minorities. Contributing for these human beings to be better, on the other hand, those who consider themselves as abiding by the law and their duties can also add value to what they already have as a posture, being able to turn their gaze and refine their listening (DUNKER and THEBAS, 2019), so that, through the examples and experiences present in the other, they can overcome the mistakes they carry in their personality.

The proposal of Restorative Justice is the non-segregation and stigmatization of people by punitive institutions, which do not come against the strengthening of relationships between human beings involved in facts where there is damage or injury to the right, but on the contrary, strengthen the network of relationships of the subject, so that he can change from his awareness of belonging, of citizenship and thus, predict and avoid criminal and bad faith practices.

In the legal system and not without reason, when there is a right injury, the primal look is turned to the offender, the same happening later, but with the effective attempt to punish him, to repay him for the wrong done. In this context, the role of the victim, family members and other members of society is restricted to reporting and witnessing the facts, nothing more. Upon receiving the punishment, the individual does not see it as a means of reflection and proposal for change, but understands what motivated him to act contrary to the legal order, which for him is enough to justify his conduct, regardless of the consequence he will bear. This reality feeds and encourages practices of this nature, so much so that many practice them repeatedly.

According to ELLIOT, 2018, p.35:

We have been challenged through these relationships to deepen our understanding of what we call “Restorative Justice” and to consider a more holistic context for conflict. This means that there is a tendency to see the promise of change as emerging from the roots of our society rather than being institutionally driven.

However, considering a more holistic context for the conflict is, at the same time, viewing possible biases for it to be materialized in this way, which presupposes the adoption of constitutional principles, Human Rights and also, seeing them as a result of the religious principles that through their foundations they can lead to change in society (SAROV, 2004), in the community, in order to compose its structure, just as violence makes up the daily lives of people in their conduct.

Changing the environment in a structural way causes the dissemination of these values, assuming, not to admit there are conducts contrary to them, not by force or state imposition, but

by an existential condition that makes up its structure, not conceiving another form of coexistence. , as is the case, for example, in Denmark (RUSSELL, 2016).

Therefore, in order to conceive Restorative Justice, paradigm shifts are necessary, needing to be constantly thought, reviewed and adapted, through the opening to dialogue, because only this is capable of enabling a circumstantial critical analysis, where family, religious formation, punishment and justice, therefore, are the social spaces where our beliefs and convictions are acquired and can influence decisions when there are conflicting facts and social consequences.

3 SUBSIDIES FOR THE ADOPTION OF RELIGIOUS PRINCIPLES IN A JUSTICE THAT WANTS TO SEE ITSELF AS RESTORATIVE

The search for a Restorative Justice or the ideal of what is fair can be seen as a reflection of religious precepts in human life from a Right of Belief that makes a Human Right effective, therefore, always having to be respected.

The right to religious belief is part of the culture of several peoples, translating checks and balances for human action, so much so that freedom of belief occupies its space in the Constitution of Brazil, and in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, therefore, the way found to if the realization of this right was made possible, it took place through the secularism that must be present in the state's action.

The Right of Belief enables the adoption of religious values that are able to provide the necessary support for a rethinking of postures, behaviors and their adoption in society, since religious belief makes us admit to be very necessary, so much so that it is recognized by law as such. , perhaps for the reason that conflicts do not only happen with those who are incorrect in their relationships, but open to all people.

SANDEL, 2011, p.307 emphasizes when citing Obama on the important role of religion and that it is in line with the proposition of a Restorative Justice that:

“Religion was not just a source of fiery political rhetoric. The solution to certain social problems required a moral transformation. The fear of falling for a 'moral sermon' can (...) lead us to downplay the role that values and culture play in some of our most pressing social problems, says Obama. Addressing problems such as 'poverty and racism, lack of health care and unemployment' would require 'changes of heart and conscience'. So it was a mistake to insist that moral and religious convictions play no role in politics or law.”

Religion is able to reconnect men to men and thus, parameterize conduct, mainly through the recognition that true justice can only happen through the law and forgiveness taken as law. The experience of granting mercy towards the common good, converges with the definition of law left by Saint Thomas Aquinas (1225-1274), as it explains the law:

I^a-IIae q. 90 a. 4 co.

Reply dicendum quod, sicut dictum est, lex imponitur aliis per modum regulae et mensurae. Regula autem et mensura imponitur per hoc quod applicatur his quae regulantur et mensurantur. Unde ad hoc quod lex virtutem obligandi obtineat, quod est proprium legis, oportet quod applicetur hominibus qui secundum eam regulari debent. Talis autem applicatio fit per hoc quod in notitiam eorum deducitur ex ipsa promulgatione. Unde promulgatio necessaria est ad hoc quod lex habeat suam virtutem. Et sic ex quatuor praedictis potest colligi definitio legis, quae nihil est aliud quam quaedam rationis ordinatio ad bonum commune, ab eo qui curam communitatis habet, promulgata.¹

Given this premise, it can be said that it is currently recognized that the fact that the person committing a crime, however barbaric it may be, does not take away his dignity as a human person. Also, it does not deprive him of the right as a human being that the Human Rights contained in the Universal Declaration are for him; which does not mean to go unpunished. Forgiveness, in this light, does not remove the condition of having to fulfill the penalty imposed on him, but rather that he must be aware of why such a sanction was applied to him and why he must fulfill it, because, from this recognition, the law will pass to this human being to have a reforming and, therefore, restorative meaning, being able to contribute to the achievement of the common good, which is nothing more than the purpose for which it was created.

However, the adoption of Restorative Justice is based on provoking in this human being a condition of true repentance, which is only possible with the adoption of religious values because it allows for a deep reflection of the legal deviations practiced that brought harmful consequences to him. as a practitioner of the infraction as for the victim and why not, if it recognizes reaching society, being a social sin as well.

The legal framework that involves this right to religious belief in Brazil must be respected and experienced fully and freely by all who conceive of it as values, otherwise the founding principle of human dignity and Human Rights will not have materialized, leading to non-effectiveness of Restorative Justice.

¹ <http://www.corpusthomisticum.org/sth2090.html>

Respect for the right and freedom of religious belief can be said to be the way to have the intended consequence in relation to the promotion of Restorative Justice, experienced from human respect, fraternity, diversity and the exercise of practices of the well, where there is room for human beings and for the human rights that belong to them.

Contrary to what has been mentioned with regard to the law and forgiveness as a condition of human dignity, FASTIGGI, 2020, teaches that there has been a change in the Catholic Church's view and on the changes in the Catechism highlights:

This new formulation of the Church's teaching on the death penalty does not obscure the Church's traditional teaching on law and justice, but applies the principle of mercy to those convicted of very serious crimes. These convicted criminals are worthy of God's mercy because they still retain human dignity and public safety can be maintained without definitively depriving these criminals of the possibility of redemption. In previous centuries, those condemned to death were believed to have hope of redemption in the next life, but they lost the right to continue to live on earth. The Church now believes that punishments should never remove hope of being reintegrated into society.

Recognition of the influence of religious belief as a major factor for Restorative Justice to become viable for our society, highlights the need to recognize the important role of the Secular State, which does not impose and adopt a common religion to Brazilian society, but does not fail to recognize what is constitutionally legalized, that is, religious freedom.

The fact of its insertion within a context that involves Justice and its application as a regulated right does not remove the possibility that it is done through the adoption of religious principles (MILAZZO, 2013) and in no way violating the characteristic of state secularism.

Therefore, it is *conditio sine qua non* for there to be a Restorative Justice to adopt religious principles, such as charity, fraternity and forgiveness, not to generate and promote impunity, but to call those who committed the infraction to responsibility, to that he has his gaze turned to the other, reflecting on the consequences of his actions, in a commitment that leads him not only to want to repair the wrong done, but also to change his posture, even feeling that he had mercy and, therefore, the look of the other and the State.

4 CONCLUSION

The adoption of religious precepts and the practice of a cult by a people has been, over time, a practice that has incorporated it as a culture, and must be preserved and guaranteed by the State, all the more so that justice, currently represented what is called Restorative Justice.

With the recognition that religious belief is a Right that has values that support it, as a result of this work, the importance of guaranteeing freedom of belief, through a secular State, as the realization of Human Rights so that one can have the effects of a Restorative Justice, which makes it possible to rescue the human essence.

In addition to this aspect and the legal guarantees that freedom of religious belief has, we believe that the set of values of a religion is the way to promote rapprochement between human beings, making it possible to achieve Restorative Justice.

Therefore, the State must maintain itself in a secular condition, so that everyone has the Human Right to choose what to believe and in the way to worship, thus respecting the diversity that exists among human beings, so that despite it they can remain united in harmonious coexistence.

The action of the State must guarantee the possibility of adopting religious beliefs, for the formation of social contexts that shelter the possibility of the offending individual to reflect on their choices, being able to become aware of their mistakes, which normally lead to recurrent practices of acts. infringements and, as a consequence, cause damage to rights.

Exercising the important role of respecting constitutional dictates and the Right to Religious Belief with freedom advocated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the State fulfills its role by "constituting(action)" to lead human beings to a free, harmonious society that recognizes everyone as worthy in their human condition as citizens who are entitled to live together for the common good.

As is recognized, Restorative Justice has its importance in the construction of a more just, humane and balanced society in its relationships, but it does not require the adoption of religious precepts in human life, guaranteed by the secular state figure, respecting the Right of Belief as a Human Right.

5 BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

ALMEIDA, Francisco José de. **The virtue of order**. 2.Ed. São Paulo: Quadrant, 2015.

CARVALHO, Fábio Tenório de. **Infer Explanations and Explain Inferences: A pragmatic-transcendental approach to inference to the best explanation**. UFMG Thesis. Available at <https://1library.org/article/abdu%C3%A7%C3%A3o-m%C3%A9todo-de-investiga%C3%A7%C3%A3o-cient%C3%ADfica.dzx5xgoq> Accessed on 11.10 .2021.

CECCHETTI, E.; OLIVEIRA, LB **“Religious diversity and human rights: knowing, respecting and living together”**. UNESP: Interdisciplinary Journal of Human Rights – RIDH, 3(1), pp. 1-18, 2015. Available at

<https://www3.faac.unesp.br/ridh/index.php/ridh/article/view/268/129> Accessed on 09.10.2021.

CURY, Carlos Roberto Jamil. **Religious education in public schools: the return of a recurring controversy.** Brazilian Journal of Education, n.27 pages 183-213. Available at <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eVrmegbbhca5x2eVK6QOuIYjh5xs4mvf/view>

UNIVERSAL DECLARATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS. Available at https://www.ohchr.org/EN/UDHR/Documents/UDHR_Translations/eng.pdf Accessed 9/13/2021.

DWORKIN, Ronald. **The fox and the porcupine: justice and valor.** Translation: Marcelo Brandão Cipolla. São Paulo: Publisher WMF Martins Fontes, 2014.

DUNKER, Christian. THEBAS, Claudio. **The Clown and the Psychoanalyst: How Listening to Others Can Transform Lives.** São Paulo: Planet of Brazil, 2019.

ELLIOT, Elizabeth M. **Safety and care: restorative justice and healthy societies.** Translation: Cristina Telles Assumpção. Sao Paulo: Palas Athena. Brasilia: Abramaj, 2018.

Fastiggi, Robert. **Law, Justice, Mercy and Forgiveness from a Catholic Perspective.** Canopy Forum, February 17, 2020. <https://canopyforum.org/2020/02/17/law-justice-mercy-and-forgiveness-from-a-catholic-perspective-by-robert-fastiggi/> Accessed 19.10 .2021.

LENNA, Pierre. **Our vision of the world: some reflections for education.** Chapter IV. The challenge of the 21st century: reconnecting knowledge. (Organized by Edgar Morin). Lisbon: Piaget, 1999.

MOM, Valter Hugo. **The dehumanization.** São Paulo: Cosacnaify, 2015.

MILAZZO, Cristhyan Martins Castro. **Restorative Justice: paths of fraternity, human rights and social dignity.** Restorative Justice: in search of brotherhood, democracy, human rights, and social dignity. 2013. 171 f. Thesis (Doctorate in Human Sciences) - Pontifical Catholic University of Goiás, GOIÂNIA, 2013. Available at <http://tede2.pucgoias.edu.br:8080/handle/tede/756> Accessed on 10.19.2021.

PEIRCE, Charles Sanders. **Semiotics.** Translation: José Teixeira Coelho Neto. São Paulo: Perspective, 2015.

PRODANOV, Cleber Cristiano. FREITAS, Ernani Cesar de. **Methodology of Scientific Work: methods and techniques of research and academic work.** 2.Ed. New Hamburg: Feevale, 2013.

RUSSELL, Helen. **Denmark's secret.** Translation: Izabel Aleixo and Léa Viveiros de Castro. Sao Paulo: Le Ya, 2016.

SANDEL, Michael J. **Justice: What it's like to do the right thing.** Translation: Heloisa Matias and Maria Alice Máximo. 4. Ed. Rio de Janeiro: Brazilian Civilization, 2011.

SAROV, Seraphim de. **The dialogue with Motovilov.** Translation: Fr. Jose Luis de Almeida Monteiro. Sao Paulo: Paulinas, 2004.

STRECK, Lenio Luiz. **Constitutional and hermeneutic jurisdiction: a new critique of law.** 2.Ed. Rio de Janeiro: Forensics, 2004.